

EVALUATION OF THE ILLUSTRATIONS AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS IN ADVERTISEMENT

DR. VANDANA N. KHEDIKAR,

I/C Principal, Dr. D Y Patil College of Applied Art & Crafts, Akurdi Pune

ABSTRACT

Illustration is the major aspect used in advertisement of product and services. Illustration comprises of drawings, photographs, maps, diagrams & etc in an advertisement. It depicts more information about the brand as well as services. It plays seminal role in communication between brand-name and consumers. During the period of 1960 to 1970, illustrations were drawn by Artists without using computer. In post 1970 period, photo illustrations were incorporated in advertisement, it is also observed that combination of illustration and photography was used in advertisements. From past two decades, computer graphics is being predominantly used in the field of advertisement. This paper covers the study of Illustrations from 1960 till date.

KEYWORDS: Illustration, Advertisement, Computer Graphics, Print Media Advertisement, Elements of art.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the prime objective of advertisement is to get wider publicity and boost the sale of particular product/services. Manufacturer assigns the job of advertising to the advertiser. Advertiser represents the utility of product in a creative manner through the advertisement. If advertisement is planned to release through print media, advertiser designs it by including pictures, typography and attractive color combinations in the layout. A picture speaks louder than words. Advertiser attempts to convey the message of that particular subject, through the illustration. Mostly print media advertisements contain illustrations. The definition of an illustration is 'a picture or a drawing or the act of creating the drawing, is to explain or prove something'. Generally illustration

means pictures however known as advertising illustration which contains photographs, maps, diagrams etc. Depending upon the theme, drawing and photograph or clubbed together to achieve the objectives behind the planned concept. Sometimes collage is also one of the preferred options. In 1960's the illustrations were in the form of manual drawing. Even products were designed in the manually. In Fig 1, the advertisement of 'ENO' is manually created, even its Visual is in form of illustration accordingly to headline is the sample of pen & ink

drawing representing sparkles. Here the artist has composed & illustrated the drawing as well as typographical part on paper then converted an artwork into photo film towards the process of preparing block in prescribed size for printing.

Fig 1.

Fig 2.

In above Fig 2., advertisement of Rajdoot motorcycle (1970's) was created manually using the cut-paste method. Visual illustration use of product is photographic and feature visuals are in detail drawing. The typography from Headline to Copy-matter is also composed accordingly.

Fig 3.

Fig 4.

In the Above Fig 3, it is shown the advertisement of Lux product in 1975. This was kind of new advertisement type which introduced through Lux campaign is a detail photographic illustration which is used in new style and the concept of **Brand Ambassador** came into existence. It is also observed that the photos used in campaign were advance of the decade. Colorful age of advertisements started in boom since 1980. As per Fig 4, in which multiple photos of SLR camera by hand finishing gave a historic turn to advertising design. This method was also based on cut-paste method of making blocks/frames. Computer Technology was new to the

world during the 1960's; in fact it was hardly introduced to India. Computer in photography was introduced in India around 1990's and its artistic use in Communication & Advertising since 1995. Advertisement designing by using computer became cheaper than before and more popular in visual artists since 2000 onward, which brought a big revolution in creative advertisement field and changed its face.

II. COMPUTER GRAPHICS AND CREATIVITY

Computer graphic software's focuses on creativity. Presenting various options to customers became feasible and faster, since editing method became simple. Artist's creativity and scope increased because of computer graphic software. Below are the few examples:

Fig 5.

Fig 6.

After studying the Advertisement of Fig 6, an art-work of background used to be created manually with spray gun in the decade of 1960 to 90 known as **vignette**. Now compute graphic software enables this effect within no-time on a single click. Typography & Photography are being edited to get creative effects as desired. In Advertisement Fig 6, the layout is simple but in product illustration i.e. mobile a rectangular object is kept in vertical position and multiple photos in symmetrical form is organized to indicate unlimited storage. 'G' of Google is created colorful as color pallet in pixel form. The Graphic design has created a sense of attraction which proved to be an important tool. Using an in detail understanding of advertising and composition, a graphic designer can make a creative and interesting piece that helps the product set out in the mind of customer.

III. ILLUSTRATION AND COMPUTER GRAPHIC

Till 1990, an artist used to work with advertisement agencies. Illustration (Drawing/Coloring) was complete handmade process during that period. But due to advancement in technologies, artists are using I-Pad/laptops to create illustration by using their ideas. Different shapes and forms were introduced through Computer graphics so illustrating creative forms

according to the concept became easier. Artist can give various effects using computer software's. This has made entire process in very convenient and less time consuming. Therefore, illustration art is now based on technologies and software available. An Artist can elaborate his/her thoughts by using computer tools and techniques. Business oriented arts are grown because of Computer graphics. Following is a List of latest graphic software available to use.

S. No.	New arts	Software used
1	Mobile game	PhotoShop, Maya, 3D Max, illustrator, iDraw
2	Animation	Moho, Synfig Studio, Pencil2D, DrawPlus
3	Film Making, Video game, DarkBASIC, DarkBASIC Pro.	VFX
4	User interface design (UID)	Altia, Adobe Primer, illustrator
5	3D Modeling	Maya, 3 D Max

Fig 7.

As the rate of literacy level is rapidly increasing, expressive typography is becoming creative and attractive with a professional touch. A Newspaper Advertisement in Fig 7, related to a city, the city name is highlighted and photographic illustration is inserted. Tint background in layout is giving the space a feel of typographical presentation. The bold expressive creation of typography and illustrative combination is an effective approach.

IV. COMPUTER GRAPHICS AND DESIGN PRINCIPLES

Advertising is an art and science which effects on readers memory with its design elements. Principles of design play an important role for effective visuals in advertisement making. **Unity, repetition, dominance balance, proximity, alignment** are main principles. Design principles can easily implemented by computer graphics. It should be eye-catching and attractive. Advertisement is a part of visual communication for seeking reader's attention. Applied artist create illustrations in his advertisement and do various experiment while designing advertising layout. More

options and changes could do with the help of computer graphic software. In Fig 8, the designs of building forms created by using the computer graphics. 'Repetition' a design principal is followed while designing this advertisement. The forms can easily move or rotated while doing designing with the click. In Fig 9, the headline of the advertisement created with the help of Corel-draw software and the red board with white letters is a perspective approach designed by computer in very less time. The readability and perfection is more appropriate compare to handmade work.

Fig 8.

Fig 9.

Fig 10.

Now a day, most of the advertisement is prepared by using computerstools/software. Illustration is an important aspect which should be incorporated in Advertisement layout. It conveys message to viewer/reader and gives information about product's USP's. It also helps to get attention of the viewer/reader because Illustrations are colorful and it attracts the human eye. Illustrations created by applied artist through computer graphic are creative, and impactful. In the Fig 10, it is an example of the new style of creative illustration. Applied artists can easily create the illustration as per the requirements by using their artistic skills. Artist's intention to incorporate illustration in the advertisement is the viewer can be informed about the product in an entertainment way to should create impression in human mind.

IV. VISUAL DESIGNS IN THE ADVERTISEMENT

Advertisement is design by artists. It is the tool of marketing and it conveys message creatively through words and pictures. These day's advertisements are made by using computer graphics and tools. Artist can

create more expressive illustrations and visual design or forms with the help of computer.

Fig 11.

In above published advertisement Fig 11, photo illustration is used. Photos of cars and behind the cars there is cervical wall designed with the visual design forms. Repetitions of circle, the curve of the wall is done by computer tool in very less time. However this can also be created manually but it will take lot of time and efforts. Now days various visual design are prepared by computer for the decoration of an advertisement.

V. FINDINGS & CONCLUSION

Researcher's collects the advertisements and observe the Illustration in the advertisements till date. The following findings are obtained.

Year	Brand	Illustration Techniques used
1960	'ENO'	Drawn by hand
1970	Rajdoot	Black and white Photograph, hand drawn drawings
1975	Lux	Black and white Photograph of model, product's photo
1980-2000	Thumps up	Multiple colored photographs
2000-2005	Print media's advertisements of all brands	Artist creates whole advertisement through their PC. Illustrations made by hands and colored whit computer software. Mostly colored photographs were used. They are edited by computer.
2005-2018	Inventz, Pixel 2, Maharashtra times, Tata moters, Honda	Blend of Illustration and typography is created. Visual design seen in the advertisement. Expressive illustration are created by computer graphic

An important aspect in advertisement, 'Illustration' emerged by computer graphics. The formation of illustration in 90's has changed, Drawings, diagrams are replaced by graphical forms. Illustrations are found in various style and design patterns are commonly found in today's advertising layout. For example, flat colors and

simplification. So complexity is avoided in visuals. Artist's creativity reaches to the highest levels when he converts the pictures from his mind into computer graphics. This has given the feature to combine various shapes in single illustration, so target audience can understand it easily. Various visual designs are included with illustration in the advertisement due to computer graphics. It is a fact that Visual Design is the new element invented by applied artist to incorporate inprint media's advertising. Illustration in the advertising is quickly prepared by using computer graphic. The artist must learn the new versions of the latest software's to create impactful illustration to sell the brands/services.

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